

PHOTOPOLYMERISATION OF FORMALDEHYDE TO REDUCING SUGARS IN VITRO.

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In publication from the laboratories, Dhar and collaborators (Dhar and Sanyal, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, **29**, 926; Gopala Rao and Dhar, *ibid.*, 1931, **35**, 1418; Atma Ram and Dhar, *ibid.*, 1932, **36**, 575) have reported the polymerisation of formaldehyde to reducing sugars, when 2 % solutions of formaldehyde to sunlight in sealed glass bulbs for periods varying from 60 to 120 hours in presence of photocatalysts like ferric chloride, chlorophyll, methyl orange, nickel carbonate, zinc oxide, etc. The best results obtained so far are those with ferric chloride. It is interesting to note, however, that formaldehyde solutions when mixed with fluorescent substances like safranin, cartharamin, rhodamin etc., are exposed to sunlight, do not form reducing sugars. Hence most of the experiments described here have been carried on with ferric chloride as a photocatalyst. In the present paper, a brief account of the results obtained is recorded.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Merck's formaldehyde after distillation was used in these experiments, since on keeping for a long time it passes into paraformaldehyde. Dilute solutions of formaldehyde with the requisite amount of ferric chloride were exposed to sunlight in thin layers in petri dishes covered with quartz covers for periods varying from 6 to 8 hours.

When a mixture of formaldehyde and ferric chloride is exposed to light, they react with the result that ferric chloride is reduced to ferrous chloride. The presence of reducing sugars photosynthesised from formaldehyde was tested by Benedict's solution, because Fehling's solution is reduced by formaldehyde also. Since ferrous chloride reduces Benedict's solution, it is necessary to remove ferrous chloride before testing the exposed solutions for reducing sugars.

To the solution after exposure, an excess of ammonia was added to remove the ferrous and ferric salts as hydroxides. The filtrate which contains ammonium salts, urotropine and the synthesised sugars, if any, was concentrated on a water-bath and evaporated to dryness. It was then extracted with methyl alcohol and the solution tested with Benedict's solution. If a

reduction was observed, the presence of reducing sugars was confirmed by Molisch's test. The amount of sugars, if sufficient, was estimated by weighing the amount of copper oxide obtained after reduction. The extracted solution was also tested for disaccharides by first hydrolysing with hydrochloric acid and then applying Benedict's test. The solution of ferric chloride should be prepared fresh and should not be acidic, but neutral as far as possible, since the presence of acids is detrimental to the polymerisation of formaldehyde to reducing sugars.

From the researches of Dhar and Palit (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, **29**, 925 ; 1928, **32**, 1262 ; 1930, **34**, 993) it is known that sugars are oxidised when their solutions are exposed to light and that ferric chloride acts as a good catalyst in these oxidation reactions. The photo-conversion of formaldehyde into reducing sugars is a slow process and it is likely that on prolonged exposure in presence of ferric chloride, the sugars synthesised may be partially photo-oxidised. In the following table some of these results are summarised.

TABLE I.

15 C.c. of 4% solution of formaldehyde exposed. Container—Petri dishes covered with quartz covers.

System exposed.	Amount of sugar as glucose in 100 c.c.		
	7 hr.	10 hr.	15 hr.
1. Formaldehyde with 2 c.c. of $N/5\text{-FeCl}_3$	0.0007	0.001	0.0012
2. " " 3 c.c. "	0.001	0.0012	0.0011
3. " " 0.5 g. of pure kieselguhr	Nil	Nil	Nil
4. Exp. No. 3 with both kieselguhr and ferric chloride	0.0013	0.0017	0.002

These results corroborate the previous claim established by us that formaldehyde can be readily converted into reducing sugars in presence of ferric chloride when exposed to light. Kieselguhr in presence of ferric chloride, when exposed to light, appears to be a good surface catalyst and photo-sensitiser for this reaction. It will be interesting to note here that Baly (*Faraday Soc. Discussion on Photo processes*, 1931, pp. 545) has prepared efficient photo-catalytic surfaces by depositing aluminium and ferric hydroxide on kieselguhr and obtained good yields of organic matter from carbon dioxide.

*Temperature Coefficient of the Photo-formation of Sugars from
Formaldehyde in vitro.*

In a previous communication (Atma Ranı and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 575) we have reported the temperature coefficient of the polymerisation of formaldehyde into sugars in the presence of ferric chloride. Since a study of temperature coefficient of this reaction has an important bearing on all findings with regard to the mechanism of photosynthesis, these experiments have been extended. In actual practice, the same procedure as described before was resorted to and the solutions were exposed in petri dishes kept at different temperatures. In order that a sufficient amount of sugars may be synthesised and estimations be correct, the solutions were exposed in several petri dishes.

TABLE II.

System exposed—15 c.c. of 4% formaldehyde and 2 c.c. of $N/5$ - $FeCl_3$.
Container—Petri dishes covered with the quartz covers.

Exp. No. 5—Blank (15 c.c. of formaldehyde with no ferric chloride).

	Wt. of sugar photosynthesised in g./100 c.c. calc. as glucose.				Temperature coefficients.		
	20°	30°	40°	50°	20-30°	30-40°	40-50°
1.	0.0006	0.001	0.001	0.0008	1.7	1.0	0.8
2.	0.0007	0.0011	0.001	0.00085	1.6	0.9	0.85
3.	0.00075	0.0012	0.00104	0.0009	1.6	0.9	0.86
4.	0.0006	0.0009	0.0009	0.0008	1.5	1.0	0.9
5.	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil

An examination of these results shows that the yield of sugars formed from formaldehyde begins to decrease or at least does not increase above 30°. It will be interesting to note here that the yield of formaldehyde obtained from the photochemical reduction of carbonic acid *in vitro* also begins to decrease beyond 30°.

DISCUSSION.

From an account of the results given in the preceding pages it will be seen that a solution of formaldehyde is not easily polymerised to sugars in

the absence of photocatalysts in sunlight, but in the presence of ferric chloride, reducing sugars are obtained even after an exposure of 6 hours. The yield of formaldehyde photosynthesised from carbon dioxide and water is not as high as that of polymerised sugars from the former in presence of ferric chloride. It appears that the first stage in photosynthesis is more difficult to be accomplished than the second one.

It seems that surfaces facilitate this photo-conversion of formaldehyde into reducing sugars, since in the presence of kieselguhr and ferric chloride, the yield of photosynthesised sugars is more than in the presence of ferric chloride alone. Recently Baly and collaborators (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1935, **B117**, 218) have succeeded in preparing photocatalytic surfaces, which have a marked photosynthetic activity by depositing freshly precipitated aluminium hydroxide, ferric and chromic hydroxides with small amounts of thorium hydroxide on finely powdered kieselguhr. That photosynthesis is essentially a heterogeneous photocatalytic reaction, appears to be supported by our experiments.

The effect of temperature on the photopolymerisation of formaldehyde into reducing sugars is in accordance with its effect upon the photochemical reduction of carbon dioxide to formaldehyde and photosynthesis *in vitro*. The yield of reducing sugars is more at 30° than at 20°, whilst at 40°, the amount of sugars photosynthesised begins to show a tendency to decrease with the result that at 50°, the temperature coefficient becomes less than unity. The explanation of this observation appears to be the same as advanced by us in the case of photosynthesis of formaldehyde from carbon dioxide investigated *in vitro*. It is probable that at a higher temperature the actual amount of sugars photosynthesised may be more, but on account of their photo-oxidation, which is proceeding simultaneously, being more pronounced at higher temperatures, the actual yield determined is less; that is why a temperature coefficient less than unity has been observed.

In this connection it will be interesting to note here that Baly has observed a decrease in the yield of organic matter photosynthesised from carbon dioxide beyond 30° *in vitro*; also van Amstel (1916) obtained the value 1.25 for a 10° rise of temperature between 24° and 36.5° in photosynthesis with *Elodea* and Sir J. C. Bose obtained the value 1.22 for a 10° rise between 20° and 30° in photosynthesis with *Hydrilla*.

The authors are of opinion that a slow speed of the photo-conversion of formaldehyde into reducing sugars investigated *in vitro* may be due to the different nature of formaldehyde produced in the plants from that of the laboratory stuff. In the plants it may be in the activated state and be easily converted into sugars. Even *in vitro* when just formed it is in the

active state and a part of it may be polymerised into sugars and another converted into the ordinary inactive variety.

Baly and Barker have differentiated this form of formaldehyde from the ordinary one by assigning to it a different structural formula (HCOH). However, recently Baly has assumed the formation of activated formaldehyde as the first product of carbon assimilation *in vitro*. It is difficult to state definitely whether formaldehyde itself polymerises into sugars or requires an extra amount of energy. However, the results recorded here show that ferric salts are efficient photocatalysts in accomplishing the second stage in photosynthesis. This may be one of the functions of iron salts present in the plant.

S U M M A R Y.

1. Photo-conversion of solutions of formaldehyde (4%) into reducing sugars in the presence of ferric chloride has been observed, when the solutions are exposed to sunlight for about eight hours contained in petri dishes.

2. Finely powdered kieselguhr appears to be a good surface catalyst for this reaction.

3. The amount of reducing sugars photosynthesised is greater at 30° than that at 20°, and at 40°, there does not appear to be any appreciable increase or decrease, whilst at 50° the yield decreases.

4. The results on the temperature coefficient of the photoformation of sugars from formaldehyde *in vitro* appear to show that the effect of temperature on photosynthesis as investigated *in vitro* and *in vivo* is similar.

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